

EFFECT OF AI-ENABLED SERVICE QUALITY ON BANKS' CUSTOMER LOYALTY: MEDIATING ROLE OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

SHITTU IBRAHIM OLADIPUPO

Department of Finance, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi.
ibroprofessor@gmail.com, 08077223399

DADA OLUWABUNMI

Department of Banking and Finance, University of Ibadan
oluwabunmijdada@yahoo.com; 08034492073

ABSTRACT

Nigerian banks have been adopting the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to satisfy their customers with the intention of continuous patronage from them. Meanwhile, it is essential to investigate if the quality of the adopted AI is capable to build loyalty in customers. The study, therefore, examined the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty. The study adopted survey research design and 385 (using Cochran's formula) questionnaires were distributed to the customers of the 7 banks that have adopted AI. 317 of the questionnaires were retrieved and subjected to structural analysis with the aid of Smart PLS. Four hypotheses were formulated and the study found that AI-enabled service quality has positive and significant effect on customer loyalty, AI-enabled service quality has positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, customer satisfaction has positive and significant effect on customer loyalty while it was as well found that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant mediating effect on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty. The study recommends that banks should religiously invest on AI-risk mitigation measures to avoid cyber-attacks, information theft and other AI-risk related attacks and they should ensure continuous evaluation of the adopted AI working system to avoid bias algorithm as a result of erroneous data output.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence-enabled Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty

JEL Codes: G19, G20, G21, G29

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer loyalty does not only enhance the continuous patronage of customers but also the possibility of referring third parties to patronize the firm. The perception of customers on the success received on product or services depends on the quality of such services which therefore ought to influence customers' satisfaction as well as their loyalty to the producer of the service (Singh, 2023). Just like every other service rendering organizations, deposit money banks need to provide quality service in order to satisfy their customers and also to earn their loyalty which will be instrumental to their sustainability. To ensure service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty, modern technological advancements have opened the door for an improvement. The use of cutting-edge technology has become more and more crucial in the dynamic world in which the banking sector is not an exemption. Light and Nwaobia (2024) described banks and other financial institutions as enabler of investment and sustainable growth of every nation, so they need to be given serious attention. The use of financial technology (fintech), has revolutionized financial institutions' customer engagement strategies and operational procedures (Klausser *et al.*, 2022). The banks use a variety of delivery channels, including telephone, mobile, ATM, and internet PC banking, to offer their services in an electronic format. Additionally, clients can use a personal computer to complete all of their banking tasks

from home without physically going to the bank. Customers can check their bank balance, pay bills, transfer funds to accounts, and apply for loans electronically with the aid of PC banking, among many other services provided by electronic banking services.

Francis-Xavier *et al.* (2024) emphasized that customer satisfaction is essential for any business success. So, provision of high-quality service is imperative to achieving customer satisfaction as well as loyalty (Paulmurugan & Nagashree (2024). They further explained that customers today anticipate that banks will use technology to provide high-quality services. So, they should use quality technology innovations as their main weapon to increase customer satisfaction which would increase loyalty. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) chatbots, which are designed to improve customer interactions and expedite banking operations, is one of the most prominent examples of this technological advancement. The impact of fintech innovations on customer loyalty has drawn a lot of attention from the research community as they continue to revolutionize the financial sector (Qadiri *et al.*, 2020).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a machine that is being simulated to operate as a human using natural language processing, data mining, robotics, computer vision, image recognition, and machine learning among others. This makes it possible for it to handle the tasks and responsibilities of bank employees and as revealed by Stephen (2024), its adoption has influenced the global business landscape significantly. Bank customers expect an online real time, personalized, and timely service at their convenient, and AI chatbots promise to deliver those features. It gives customers the opportunity to communicate with the bank in order to make online and real time enquiry and complete online banking transactions among others. Artificial intelligence therefore performs these tasks with the aid of speech and facial expression recognition technologies. AI therefore has the potential of transforming the banking industry by improving quality, enhancing customers' satisfaction and loyalty (Shakyawar & Shakya, 2024).

The DeLone and McLean Information System (IS) Success Model inspired this study (DeLone & McLean, 2003) as it proposes that the success, satisfaction and loyalty of customers rely on the quality of the system like that of an AI-enabled services, by ensuring that technical difficulties, semantic problems as well as efficacy problems are avoided. Nigeria's Banking sector is highly competitive and they must ensure that they meet up with the global financial innovation. The sector is becoming so complex with huge customer base and banks must ensure that they convince customer to continue patronizing them to keep relevant in business hence, the need for AI to render their services. These are rendered through AI-enabled personalized financial service, customer support, enhanced security services, fraud detection, predictive analytics credit scoring and algorithm trading and investment management, among others. Despite the huge cost involved, banks adopt AI to ensure that they retain their customer through their loyalty. However, it is pertinent to understand if these AI-enabled services provided by the banks are of good quality and could actually influence customers' loyalty if moderated by customer satisfaction. Hence the need to examine the effect of AI-enabled Service Quality on Nigeria's Deposit Money Banks' customer loyalty: mediating role of customer satisfaction.

This study, unlike the previous studies, extends the existing literature on Artificial Intelligence-enabled services quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty as a contribution. Firstly, this study offers a comprehensive perspective on e-service quality by extending the service quality (SERVQUAL) model by Parasuraman *et al.* (1985) as it is not suitable for AI-enabled services. So, the AI-SERVQUAL which is an adaption of the study of Paulo *et al.* (2019) and the AICSQ (Artificial Intelligence Chatbots Service Quality) scale of Chen *et al.* (2022), is a great contribution of the study. Secondly, there have been several researches on AI adoption on performance, customer satisfaction and loyalty but research on AI-enabled service quality

in Bauchi and Nigeria at large has been scarcely found. Thirdly, unlike few researches conducted in Nigeria on AI that used SPSS for analysis, the study adopted Smart-PLS alongside SPSS for a robust analysis to strengthen the model.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

The theoretical frameworks and models put forth by Parasuraman *et al.* (1985), and Paulmurugan and Nagashree (2024), and Hang *et al.* (2024), all address service quality dimensions on satisfaction, performance and loyalty. The value that customers expect from a service before using it and the value they perceive after using it are compared in order to assess the quality of the service. The difference between a customer's expectations and perceptions following a service is what Harith (2019) refers to as service quality. However, several researchers working on service quality widely adopt Parasuraman's service quality measurements which are tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. This study however modifies the model as it involves Artificial Intelligent (AI), so a construct like tangibility is not applicable while some other constructs required (described in the study theoretical framework) are not included.

AI can be described as a machine made from a computer system which could perform tasks with human intelligence. It uses technologies like robotics, data mining, natural language processing, voice and image recognition, and machine learning among others. AI has been adopted by various industries like banks, to ensure that they are able to serve their numerous customers while maintaining good service quality that could enhance customer satisfaction as well as loyalty.

The use of AI has been predominant in banks like every other industry to enhance customer service delivery. Meanwhile, El-Shihy *et al.*, (2024) emphasized that the quality of an AI-enabled services cannot yet be compared to that of humans as it is lagging behind. It was therefore suggested by Suhel *et al.* (2020) that organizations like banks, should regularly evaluate and examine their AI-enabled service quality to ensure that their mission of using it is maintained.

As pointed by Johnson *et al.* (2023), Chen *et al.* (2022), Adam *et al.* (2021), Hilbert, (2020), and Paulo *et al.* (2019); the regular five (5) service quality dimensions is not applicable for AI-enabled service quality measurement and therefore highlighted other dimensions, which have the tendency of identifying improvement of AI-enabled services capabilities. The dimensions recommended are therefore response accuracy, accessibility, personalization, self-learning, consistency, empathy, availability, ease of use, and availability of human service alternatives, fulfillment and assurance (security) which are used for this study.

AI-enabled Service Quality and Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty, which is crucial for any successful business, like bank, is the extent to which consumers are committed to a particular brand or organization. Consumers who are loyal to an organisation are more likely to recommend it to others, give positive reviews, and keep patronizing them. According to Khan *et al.* (2021), this could lead to increased revenue, lower marketing expenses, and a better reputation in the marketplace. AI is being used by banks to enhance customer service. It can provide self-service and handle large volumes of requests. However, in order to foster client loyalty, AI must deliver quality and exceptional customer service. AI that is unable to respond to questions or satisfy consumers may harm the reputation of the bank. Unpleasant AI interactions have the potential to reduce loyalty over time. As a

result, banks need to create AI that can handle complicated requests, comprehend linguistic nuances, and react promptly. Customer loyalty can be increased by AI that offer friendly, seamless support and quality service. An AI that is always available could give consumers the impression that the brand values them. The ease of use of an AI could boost brand advocacy, repeat business, and customer retention. AI might be able to tailor interactions according to users' preferences and past search activity as it's been used and at the same time AI with personalized experience management could help brands stand out and boost consumer loyalty, hence, the first hypothesis is stated as:

H₀₁: AI-enabled service quality has no significant effect on customer loyalty.

AI-enabled Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

The sustainability of an organization is significantly influenced by customer satisfaction. When customers are happy with a company's products, they are more likely to make more purchases from that company, spread positive word-of-mouth about it, and not switch to a rival. It is crucial to identify and meet the needs and demands of the intended recipients in order to achieve high levels of customer satisfaction (Hult *et al.* 2022). An important factor to take into consideration is how AI-enabled service quality affects bank's customer satisfaction as most banks use them as a service delivery channel. Higher customer satisfaction is probably the result of AI-enabled service that responds quickly, pertinently, and understandably.

Customers may become unhappy with AI that have trouble interacting with natural language or that are unable to fix problems. To increase customer satisfaction, AI must provide high-quality services. A customer's experience is influenced by a number of factors, including response accuracy, response speed, communication clarity, and the capacity to handle various query types. Customers may become irritated and have a negative opinion of the brand if they have poor AI-enabled service interactions. Conversely, AI that can effectively manage routine requests can contribute to increased customer satisfaction. Customers find value and convenience in being able to obtain prompt responses from an AI-enabled service regarding product details, order status, or account information at any time and from any location.

AI has the potential to improve customer satisfaction by streamlining service and providing effective self-help options, particularly for simpler requests. Advanced natural language skills and a greater comprehension of context and semantics should result in increasingly realistic and fulfilling chat conversations as AI-enabled service develop further which could greatly raise customer satisfaction levels. This therefore enhances the formulation of the second hypotheses as thus:

H₀₂: AI-enabled service quality has no significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty and customer satisfaction are closely related concepts. A happy consumer is more likely to be loyal towards a business or brand. However, since satisfaction with a single purchase does not guarantee continuous patronage or recommendations to third parties, a satisfied customer does not always display loyal behaviors. Future choices may be influenced by additional elements like cost or the availability of alternatives (Salam *et al.* 2022). Furthermore, different customers and situations may require different levels of satisfaction in order to elicit loyalty. For instance, one customer may be permanently turned off by a small complaint, while another may choose to ignore it. However, it is essential to confirm if loyalty of customer is as a result of his or her satisfaction, hence the formulation of the third hypothesis as thus:

H₀₃: Customer satisfaction has no significant effect on customer loyalty.

Mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty

AI-enabled services are being used by banks to render basic services like inquiries and provide customer support among others. Research suggests that customer satisfaction may be impacted by AI-enabled services quality. Users may be satisfied if AI-enabled services are intelligent, responsive, user-friendly, and adept at resolving issues. AI-enabled services that mislead or don't comprehend users' requests could make them unsatisfied. Brand loyalty may be impacted by how satisfied customers are with the AI-enabled services. Customer opinions of the company may improve if their interactions with AI-enabled services are satisfactory. Customer satisfaction with AI-enabled services increases the likelihood that they will develop strong emotional bonds, trust, and brand loyalty. Even though other brand interactions are positive, bad AI-enabled services experiences can reduce customer satisfaction and brand loyalty (Tsai *et al.* 2021). Therefore, customer satisfaction and loyalty ought to be impacted by the quality of AI-enabled services, hence, the need for the formulation of the fourth hypothesis as thus:

H₀₄: Customer satisfaction does not significantly mediate the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty.

2.2 Empirical Review

The effect of AI on customers' satisfaction of Deposit Money banks in Lagos was examined by Olumoyegun *et al.* (2024). The study which focuses on the electronic payment system and robotic advisory system as a measurement of AI adopts multistage sampling techniques. Questionnaires were distributed to 385 customers of the 4 selected banks (GTBank, UBA, First Bank and Zenith Bank) used multiple regression analyses with the aid of SPSS to analyze the collected data and it was found that both electronic payment system and robotic advisory system has positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction in Lagos state. The study recommends that banks should organize awareness programs on the use of AI to the customers.

Hang *et al.* (2024) examined the impact of loan service quality on the satisfaction of SME owners in Vietnamese banks. Survey research was adopted by distributing 411 questionnaires to SME owners, out of which 376 were retrieved and subjected to analysis using PLS-SEM. The study revealed that the five (5) measurements of loan service quality (that is, reliability, empathy, tangibility, assurance and responsiveness) positively influence SMEs' satisfaction.

A study on the impact of AI on banks performance in Abuja was also investigated by Okoliko *et al.* (2023). The study is a survey research where questionnaires were distributed to 135 staff of the five (5) selected banks in Federal capital Territory of Abuja. Census sampling technique was adopted while the data received were analysed with multiple regression analysis with the aid of SPSS. It was found that AI adoption enhances bank performance and the study recommends that customers needs to be educated on the use of AI for better performance.

Anddison *et al.* (2023) examined the relationship between AI adoption and Banks performance in Rivers state with focus on customer satisfaction, economic performance and effective decision making. To achieve the objectives of the study, 110 questionnaires were distributed to the managers of the 22 banks in the state. Using correlation analysis with the aid of SPSS, the study found that AI has a positive and strong correlation with customer satisfaction, economic performance as well as the bank's decision making. It was recommended that AI should be fully adopted to further enhance decision making.

Fida *et al.* (2020) conducted research on service quality, customer loyalty and customer satisfaction in Oman Islamic Banks adopting ServQual model. The study adopted a survey method by administering questionnaire to 120 customers of the four main banks in Oman.

Correlation and regression analysis were used to analyse the collected data using SPSS. The correlation analysis revealed a significant relationship between service quality, customer loyalty and customer satisfaction while the regression analysis found that responsiveness and empathy have a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction. The study therefore recommends that banks should really focus on responsiveness and empathy, though shouldn't neglect other dimensions.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

This study adapts the study of Elshihy et al. (2024) as well as other authors that emphasized on service quality that is been enhanced by either electronic means or Artificial Intelligence. Ai et al. (2018) described the importance of the ability of AI-enabled service to be able to answer personalized questions based on the history of customers' activities (Personalisation), while the need for quality AI-based services to be accessible across different platforms and channels (accessibility) was highlighted by Hilbert (2020). Adam et al. (2021) also emphasized that a quality AI-enabled service should be able to improve itself by training on data available on the platform over time (Self-learning) which would enhance customers experience while Park and Kim (2023) as well explained the importance of easy navigation and friendliness (ease of use) of AI-enabled service platforms to customer satisfaction and loyalty. Considering all the dimensions for AI-service enabled quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, the study conceptual framework is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Framework of AI-enabled Service Quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

A coherent theoretical framework for this study rests on the logic that AI-enabled service quality shapes customer satisfaction, which in turn drives loyalty. This relationship is grounded in both complementary service and technology adoption theories. The major theory is the SERVQUAL Model, which conceptualises service quality as a multidimensional construct

comprising reliability, assurance, responsiveness, and empathy (Parasuraman *et al.*, 1985). In an AI-enabled banking context, these dimensions are reinterpreted through intelligent systems: reliability reflects system accuracy and consistency, assurance emerges from perceived security and trust in AI decisions, responsiveness is expressed through real-time automated interactions, and empathy is approximated via personalisation and adaptive interfaces. The SERVQUAL theory provides the foundation for linking perceived service quality to customer satisfaction.

To strengthen the explanatory power in a digital environment, the framework integrates the Technology Acceptance Model. This theory explains how perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use influence users' acceptance of technology-driven services (Stephen, 2024). AI features such as accessibility, ease of use, and self-learning capabilities directly shape these perceptions. When customers find AI banking services efficient, intuitive, and adaptive, they are more likely to evaluate the service positively, reinforcing satisfaction.

The mediating mechanism is best explained using the Expectation-Confirmation Theory. This theory posits that satisfaction arises when actual service performance meets or exceeds prior expectations. In AI-enabled banking, customers approach services with expectations regarding speed, accuracy, and personalisation. When AI systems deliver superior performance through predictive assistance, seamless interactions, and tailored recommendations, confirmation occurs, which will lead to satisfaction.

Synthesising these theories, the framework proposes that AI-enabled service quality influences customer loyalty indirectly through customer satisfaction. The integration of service quality, technology acceptance, and expectation-confirmation logics provides a robust explanation of how AI transforms banking experiences into sustained customer relationships.

3.2 Research Design

The study employs survey research design approach to examine the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled Service Quality and Deposit Money Banks' customer loyalty. The research focused on customers of all Deposit Money Banks that uses AI at one time or the other. Hence, the population of the study was considered infinite as the actual total number of customers of the banks cannot be ascertained from the bank. The Cochran's formula for infinite population was therefore adopted as shown in equation 1 and the sample size was estimated to be 385.

$$\frac{Z^2 * P * (1 - P)}{e^2} \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 1}$$

$$= \frac{1.96^2 * 0.5 * (1 - 0.5)}{0.05^2} = \frac{3.8416 * 0.5 * 0.5}{0.0025} = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} = 384.16 = 385$$

The questionnaires were distributed using convenience sampling technique by using the google form in order to attain the sample size calculated. The research instrument was divided into 2 Parts. The first part (Part A) looked into the demographic information of the respondents, which comprise of the age, gender, and qualification. The second part (Part B) which examined the constructs was divided into 3 sections. Section A focused on AI-enabled service quality dimensions; Section B looked into customer satisfaction items while Section C examined questions on customer loyalty and the questionnaire was designed using 5-likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5).

Questions on Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness, and Empathy were adapted from Fida *et al.* (2020) and Haitham *et al.* (2024). Personalisation was adapted from Ai *et al.* (2018) while accessibility was culled from Hilbert (2020) while items used to measure self-learning was

framed from Adam *et al.* (2021) while ease of use was adapted from Park and Kim (2023). Constructs on customer satisfaction were adapted from Paulo *et al.* (2019) and Haitham *et al.* (2024) while customer loyalty was also culled from Singh *et al.* (2023). The questionnaires were distributed to the customer and retrieved at each visit through the customer service and transaction officers’ support. Total of 317 questionnaires was correctly filled, retrieved and subjected to analysis using descriptive statistics for the demographic information and multiple regressions for the constructs with the aid of SPSS as well as Smart PLS.

3.3 Model Specification

Model specification investigates the various steps of defining the mathematical structure that represents the correlation between the dependent, independent and moderating variables. The study model is therefore specified using Structural Equation Model as thus;

$$CL = \alpha + \beta_1 AISQ + \beta_2 CS + \beta_3 (AISQ \times CS) + e \dots\dots \text{equation 3}$$

Where:

CL= Customer’s Loyalty

AISQ = Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Service Quality

CS = Customers’ Satisfaction

α = Constant Parameter (Intercept)

β_1, β_2 = Parameters to be estimated

β_3 = Moderating effect

e = Error Term

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Demographic Analyses

The items of the 317 retrieved questionnaires were coded and carefully entered into SPSS version 29. However, errors and missing data were appropriately checked to avoid outliers. This was done using descriptive statistics and no missing values were found. Descriptive statistics were conducted and it was discovered that majority of the respondents (212 people) who represent 66.9% of the customers are male while the remaining 105 people (33.1%) are female. The sample was made up of 107 people (33.8%) who fall within the age of 18 and 30. Most of the respondents (that is, 163 representing 51.4%) are between the age of 31 and 50 while other respondents (47 people, representing 14.8%) are above 50 years. Regarding the respondents academic qualification, majority of the sampled customer (149 people, representing 47.0%) have HND/BSc certificate. 33.1% (105 respondents) possess Diploma/OND certificate while others (63, representing 19.9%) have not higher than SSCE qualification.

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

Items		Frequency	Percentage
Gender:	Male	212	66.9%
	Female	105	33.1%
Age:	18-30	107	33.8%
	31-50	163	51.4%
	Above 50	47	14.8%
Qualification:	Below SSCE	63	19.9%

Diploma/ OND	105	33.1%
HND/ BSc	149	47.0%

Source: Extracted from IBM SPSS V. 29 Output, 2025.

4.2 Preliminary Tests

To ensure the suitability of the research instrument, the items used were subjected to reliability and validity test through confirmatory factor analysis. Cronbach’s Alpha (CA), rho_A and composite reliability, CR (rho_c) which were used for reliability test showed a value of above 0.7 which is an indication that the research instrument is reliable while rho_A and rho_c value of above 0.7 further indicate the robustness of the measurement model. Average Variance Explained (AVE) and factor loadings (FL) and VIF Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) were also used for validity. The AVE which range between 0.56 and 0.64 met the threshold of 0.5 while the value of VIF which were between 1.47 and 2.958 as shown in Table 2 also met the required threshold of less than 3.0 as described by Hair *et al.* (2014).

Table 2: Preliminary Tests

Constructs	Items	FL	VIF	CA	CR	AVE
AI Quality Service	AIQS1	0.845	3.048	0.901	0.919	0.56
	AIQS2	0.698	2.062			
	AISQ5	0.802	2.958			
	AISQ8	0.731	2.510			
	AISQ9	0.78	2.544			
	AISQ10	0.636	1.885			
	AISQ11	0.684	1.838			
	AISQ16	0.795	2.400			
	AISQ17	0.740	2.439			
Customer Satisfaction	CS3	0.678	1.627	0.832	0.882	0.601
	CS5	0.908	2.197			
	CS7	0.809	1.470			
Customer Loyalty	CL1	0.728	1.458	0.731	0.844	0.646
	CL3	0.765	1.809			
	CL4	0.838	1.627			
	CL6	0.847	2.227			
	CL8	0.686	1.601			

Source: Extracted from Smart PLS Output, 2025.

4.3 Testing of Hypotheses

The four hypotheses formulated to examine the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty are tested having met the requirement of the preliminary tests conducted. The result is therefore shown in Figure 1 and table 3.

Figure: Structural Model of the mediating effect of customer satisfaction

Table 3: Model Measurement Results

Constructs (H ₀)	Coefficient	SE	t-stat	P-Value	Decision
AISQ -> CL	0.623	0.155	4.019	0.044	Rejected
AISQ -> CS	0.728	0.027	29.9629	0.000	Rejected
CS -> CL	0.268	0.158	1.6962	0.000	Rejected

Source: Extracted from Smart PLS Output, 2025.

The first hypothesis tends to test the effect AI-enabled service quality on customer loyalty in Deposit Money Banks in Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi state. The test was conducted with the aid of Partial Least Square (Smart PLS) and the result of the model is revealed in Table 3 and figure 1. The result revealed coefficient (β) value of 0.623 and P value of 0.044 which is significant. The coefficient value of 0.623 therefore indicated that AI-enabled service quality explains and AI-enabled service quality has no significant effect on customer loyalty contributes 62.3% of the variance of customer loyalty while the remaining 37.7 of customer loyalty is explained by other variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and thus; AI-enabled service quality has positive and significant effect on customer loyalty.

The second hypothesis on the other hand examined the effect of AI-enabled service quality on customer satisfaction. The coefficient (β) value and P value was revealed in table 3 as 0.728 and 0.000 respectively. The result therefore indicated that there is a positive and significant relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer satisfaction which translates that 72.8% of customer satisfaction is explained by AI-enabled service quality. The third hypothesis on the other hand assesses the effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty. The coefficient (β) value of the model is 0.268 while the P value as depicted in table 3 is 0.000. This shows that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4: Mediation Result

Constructs (H ₀)	Coefficient	SE	t-stat	P-Value	Decision
AISQ -> CS -> CL	0.276	0.140	1.974	0.045	Rejected

Source: Extracted from Smart PLS Output, 2025.

Mediating analysis was conducted to test the fourth hypothesis, which is to examine the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty in Deposit Money Banks in Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi state. The result as depicted in table 4 revealed the mediating effect of AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty with the inclusion of customer satisfaction and the result revealed a coefficient (β) value of 0.276 and P value of less than 0.05 which is positive and significant. This therefore indicated a complementary partial mediation. Therefore, it was concluded that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant mediating effect on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty.

To further strengthen the mediating effect, the variance accounted for (VAF) was further evaluated as recommended by Hair *et al.* (2014). This was conducted to determine the extent at which customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty. VAF was used to further ascertain the existence of partial or full mediation within the study using the formula formulated by Hair *et al.* (2014) as thus:

$$VAF = \frac{a*b}{a*b+c}$$

Where

a = coefficient value between AI-enabled service quality and customer satisfaction

b = coefficient value between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty

c = coefficient value between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty

Therefore, the Variance Accounted For is;

$$VAF = \frac{0.728 * 0.268}{0.728 * 0.268 + 0.623}$$

$$VAF = \frac{0.1951}{0.1951 + 0.623}$$

$$VAF = \frac{0.1951}{0.8181}$$

$$VAF = 0.2385 = 23.9\%$$

The result therefore indicated that 23.9% of the total effect of the effect of AI-enabled service quality on customer loyalty has been explained by the mediating variable (customer satisfaction). According to Hair *et al.* (2014), there is no mediation if the value of VAF is less than 20%, while VAF value of between 20% and 80% indicates partial mediation and VAF value of above 80% indicates a full mediation. The VAF value of 23.9% arrived at from the study further affirmed that there is a partial mediation. Therefore, it was concluded that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant mediating effect on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The study examined the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty in Deposit Money Banks in Bauchi metropolis of Bauchi state. For the study to be achieved, four (4) major objectives and hypotheses were formulated. Hypothesis one was to examine the significant effect of AI-enabled service quality on customer loyalty. The hypotheses were subjected to structural model analysis with the aid of Smart PLS and were found that AI-enabled service quality has positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. This indicated that if AI-enabled service quality is improved upon customers will be more loyal to the bank and will continue patronizing the bank which will improve their sustainability. It was as well discovered that some customers are not aware of the existence of AI-enabled services which is available and accessible by different channels. The result is supported by El-shihy (2024) and Hang (2024) who emphasized on the need for an improved AI chatbots for customer loyalty in both banks and small and medium enterprises respectively. It is also in line with the study of Aniwetalu and Fagnemide (2025), whose study also found a positive and significant impact of service quality through promptness, courtesy and after-sales-service on customer's loyalty. On the other hand, the second hypotheses investigated the effect of AI-enabled service quality on customer satisfaction. The hypothesis which was also tested by structural model revealed that AI-enabled service quality has positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. This means that AI-enabled service quality has a direct relationship with customer satisfaction. It implies that if customers experience quality services from Artificial Intelligence adopted by banks, the customer will be fulfilled and satisfied. Customers however were discovered to be scared of been experiencing a secured and confidential activities using AI-enabled services. These findings were supported by Fida *et al.* (2020) and Adam *et al.* (2021). This also corroborate the study of Kabiru *et al.* (2023), whose study revealed that all service quality dimensions are positive and statistically significant to customer satisfaction.

The effect of Customer satisfaction on customer loyalty was hypothesized as the third hypothesis and it was found that customer satisfaction has positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. This implies that if customers are satisfied, they will not only want to come back to the bank for continuous service but will also refer third party to the bank. This was supported by the work of Fida *et al.* (2020) and that of Hang (2024). The fourth hypothesis which is the main hypothesis examined the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty. The hypothesis was tested with the aid of bootstrapping through the consistent PLS algorithm and was found that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant mediating effect on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty. This implies that customers have to be satisfied with the quality of AI-enabled services for them to continuously be patronising the brand and also refer third parties. Banks should ensure that they provide quality AI-enabled service that could make customers to be fulfilled and thereby influence their loyalty. It was as well discovered that less quality AI-enabled services could possess a bias algorithm through an erroneous data output. These findings were in line with El-Shihy (2024) as well as Adam *et al.* (2021). It also corroborates the study of Ayinaddis (2023), who investigated the effect of e-banking service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The study found a positive and significant effect of electronic banking service quality on customer's satisfaction. It also revealed a positive and significant effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty and finally showed that customer satisfaction has a mediating effect on the relationship between e-banking service quality and customer's loyalty. However, it contradicts the study of Supriyanto *et al.* (2021) whose study though support the direct effect of service quality on customer satisfaction, but found an indirect effect of service quality on customer loyalty. Meanwhile, the

scope of the study's service quality is limited to the traditional service quality and not digital service quality like AI.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study examined the the mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty in Deposit Money Banks. The study adapted AI-enabled service quality dimensions as well as that of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty from reputable researchers. The study is survey research where 385 questionnaires were distributed to customers of Deposit Money Banks in Bauchi. 317 of the distributed were retrieved and subjected to analysis using Smart PLS. The study found that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant mediating effect on the relationship between AI-enabled service quality and customer loyalty. This study significantly contributes to the existing knowledge in the field of AI, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty and generally it provides practical insight on how bank practitioners should manage AI-enabled services to enhance loyalty. A potential recommendation for future research in this field is to examine the individual dimension of AI-Service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty.

5.2 Policy Recommendations

The study therefore recommends the following based on the findings of the study:

1. Banks management should continuously organise awareness programs on the availability and use of AI-enabled services in banks to further maximise its use.
2. Banks should religiously invest on AI-risk mitigation measures to avoid cyber attacks, information theft and other AI-risk related attacks.
3. Banks should ensure continuous evaluation of the adopted AI working system to avoid bias algorithm as a result of erroneous data output

REFERENCES

- Adam, M., Wessel, M., & Benlian, A. (2021). AI-based chatbots in customer service and their effects on user compliance. *Electronic Markets*, 31(2), 427-445. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-020-00414-7>
- Ai, Q., Azizi, V., Chen, X., & Zhang, Y. (2018). Learning heterogeneous knowledge base embeddings for explainable e recommendation. *Algorithms*, 11(9), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/a11090137>
- Addison, E. C., Joseph, B. N., & Uelee, M. N. (2013). Artificial Intelligence adoption and organizational performance of Money Deposit Banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Information Systems Research*, 4(April), 6-17.
- Aniwetalu, I. C., & Fagbemide, O. S. (2015). Influence of corporate image, perceived value, and service quality on customer loyalty to indigenous brands in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 10(3), 175-184.
- Ayinaddis, S.G., Taye, B.A. & Yirsaw, B.G. (2023). Examining the effect of electronic banking service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty: an implication for technological innovation. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 12(22), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-023-00287-y>
- Chen, Y., Li, T., & Tang, F. (2022). Exploring the dimensions of AI chatbot service quality: An empirical study. *Information & Management*, 59(1), 103516. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t89688-000>

- Delone, W., & McLean, E. (2003). The DeLone and McLean Model of Information Systems Success: A Ten-Year Update, *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 19(4), 9-30. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/07421222.2003.11045748>
- El-Shihy, D., Abdelraouf, M., Hegazy, M., & Hassan, N. (2024). The Influence of AI Chatbots in Fintech Services on Customer Loyalty within the Banking Industry. *Future of Business Administration*, 3(1), 16-28. <https://doi.org/10.33422/fba.v3i1.644>
- Fida, B. A., Ahmed, U., Al-Balushi, Y., & Singh, D. (2020). Impact of service quality on customer loyalty and customer satisfaction in Islamic banks in the sultanate of Oman. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020919517>
- Francis-Xavier, I. O., Nkemdilim, I. & Chibueze, C., Sheneni, F. M. (2024). Customer satisfaction survey of the Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) service in Lagos. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(1), 352-376.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2014). *Multivariate data analysis* (7th ed.). Pearson Education Limited.
- Haitham, H. A., Asma, A., Rafea, M., & Murad Y. A. (2024). Examining the mediating role of customer empowerment: the impact of chatbot usability on customer satisfaction in Jordanian commercial banks, *Cogent Business & Management*, 11:1, 2387196, DOI:10.1080/23311975.2024.2387196
- Hang, N. P., & Trung N. K. (2024). Service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty: A case study in Vietnamese SMEs. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2377769>
- Harith, Y. K., Ahmad, J., & Abbas, M. (2019). Review of scoping studies on service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in the airline industry. *Contemporary Economics*, 13(4), 375-387.
- Hilbert, M. (2020). Digital technology and social change: the digital transformation of society from a historical perspective. *Dialogues in clinical neuroscience*, 22(2), 189-194. <https://doi.org/10.31887/DCNS.2020.22.2/mhilbert>
- Hult, G. T. M., Neese, W. T., & Bashaw, R. E. (2022). The relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty: A moderated mediation model. *Journal of Business Research*, 141, 491-501.
- Johnson, D., Goodman, R., Patrinely, J., Stone, C., Zimmerman, E., Donald, R., ... & Wheless, L. (2023). Assessing the accuracy and reliability of AI-generated medical responses: an evaluation of the Chat-GPT model. Research square. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2566942/v1>
- Kabiru, H., Abdulsalam, S., & Jika, U. (2023). Service quality in hotels: Understanding customers' perceptions for improved guest satisfaction. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 8(2), 49-59.
- Khan, M. L., Al-Jabri, I. M., & Al-Shihi, H. (2021). Exploring the impact of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty in the banking sector. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 39(6), 1333-1354.
- Klausser, V. J., Salamapasis, D., & Kaiser, A. (2022). Driving the Future of FinTech-led Transformation in Financial Services: Business Trends and the New Face of Open Innovation. In *Transformation Dynamics in FinTech: An Open Innovation Ecosystem Outlook* (pp. 127-159). https://doi.org/10.1142/9789811239731_0005
- Light, C., & Nwaobia, G. E. (2024). Impact of financial institutions on economic activities in Nigeria (a case study of commercial banks located in Owerri municipal, Nigeria). *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(4), 239-254.
- Okoliko, E.O., Ayetigbo, O. A., Ifegwu, I. J., & Chidiebere, N.U. (2023). Artificial Intelligence Impact in Revolutionizing the Nigerian Banking Industry: An Assessment of Selected Deposit Money Banks in Abuja. *Achievers Journal of Scientific Research*, 5(2), 120-131.
- Olumoyegun, P. M., Alabi, J. O., & Nurudeen, Y. Z. (2024). Artificial Intelligence and customer satisfaction of selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos state, Nigeria. *Journal of Business Management, Innovation and Creativity*, 3(2), 178-189.

- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1985). A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), 41-50
- Park, D. Y., & Kim, H. (2023). Determinants of intentions to use digital mental healthcare content among university students, faculty, and staff: motivation, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and parasocial interaction with AI Chatbot. *Sustainability*, 15(1), 872. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010872>
- Paulmurugan, S., & Nagashree, M. (2024). Customer perception towards AI Chatbots acceptance in Bangalore: An empirical investigation among Banks. *Migration Letters*, 1(5), 198-204.
- Paulo, R., Tiago, O., Almira, F. (2019). The impact of e-service quality and customer satisfaction on customer behavior in online shopping. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02690>
- Qadiri, R. M., Shabir, N., & Qadri, M. (2020). Conceptualizing possibilities of artificial intelligence in furtherance of the banking sector: an effective tool for improving customer relationship, customer service and public relations.
- Salam, M. A., Azam, M. N., Rahman, M. M., & Uddin, M. J. (2022). The impact of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty: Evidence from the banking industry. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics, and Business*, 9(5), 201-211.
- Shakyawar, M., & Shakya, K. (2024). Using Artificial Intelligence to Improve Banking Services in India: A Review and Prospects for the Future. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology*, 12(4), 728-738.
- Singh, V., Sharma, M., Jayapriya, K., & Kumar, B. (2023). Service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: A comprehensive literature review. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Science*, 10(4S) 3457-3464.
- Stephen, O. O. (2024). Impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on the growth of startups in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(4), 1-16.
- Suhel, S. F., Shukla, V. K., Vyas, S., & Mishra, V. P. (2020, June). Conversation to automation in banking through chatbot using artificial machine intelligence language. In 2020 8th international conference on reliability, infocom technologies and optimization (trends and future directions) (ICRITO) (pp. 611-618). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRITO48877.2020.9197825>
- Supriyanto, A., Wiyono, B. B., & Burhanuddin, B. (2021). Effects of service quality and customer satisfaction on loyalty of bank customers. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2021.1937847>
- Tsai, W. H. S., Liu, Y., & Chuan, C. H. (2021). How chatbots' social presence communication enhances consumer engagement: the mediating role of parasocial interaction and dialogue. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 15(3), 460-482. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIM-12-2019-0200P>